

COMPONENTS' AND MATERIALS' PERFORMANCE FOR ADVANCED SOLAR SUPERCRITICAL CO₂ POWERPLANTS

Testing and degradation mechanisms of bulk and optimized particles

Deliverable Number 2.3

WP2

Date: 30.4.2024

Deliverable type: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Lead participant: DLR

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. **958418**.

AUTHORS

Name	Organization
Florian Sutter	DLR
Gözde Alkan	DLR
Florian Wiesinger	DLR
Ana Cleia Gonzalez Alves	DLR
Gema San Vicente	CIEMAT
Angel Morales	CIEMAT
Arantxa Fernandez Garcia	CIEMAT
Samuel Marlin	Saint-Gobain
Nassira Benameur	Saint-Gobain
Mathias Galetz	Dechema Forschungsinstitut
Michael Kerbstadt	Dechema Forschungsinstitut
Ceyhun Oskay	Dechema Forschungsinstitut
Christoph Grimme	Dechema Forschungsinstitut

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Change
01	30.4.2024	Initial version uploaded

ABOUT THE PROJECT

COMPASSCO₂ is a 4-year HORIZON2020 project started on 1.11.2020. It is led by the German Aerospace Center (DLR), with eleven additional partners from seven European countries.

COMPASSCO₂ aims to integrate CSP particle systems into highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production. In COMPASSCO₂, the key component for such an integration, i.e. the particle/s-CO₂ heat exchanger, will be validated in a relevant environment. To reach this goal, the consortium will produce tailored particle and alloy combinations that meet the extreme operating conditions in terms of temperature, pressure, abrasion and hot oxidation/carburization of the heat exchanger tubes and the particles moving around/across them. The proposed innovative CSP s-CO₂ Brayton cycle plants will be flexible, highly efficient, economic and 100% carbon neutral large-scale electricity producers.

The research focus of COMPASSCO₂ is on three main technological improvements: development of new particles, development of new metal alloys and development of the heat exchanger section.

DISCLAIMER

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. **958418**.

The content of this publication reflects only the author's view and not necessary those of the European Commission. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Figures.....	4
List of Tables.....	5
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Abstract.....	6
2 Thermal exposure testing (DLR/CIEMAT)	6
2.1 static thermal testing in furnace up to 4000h and 1000°c.....	6
2.2 cyclic thermal testing in furnace up to 3000h and 1000°c (DFI)	11
3 Environmental testing (condensation and freezing conditions) (DLR/CIEMAT).....	17
4 Abrasion and mechanical testing at ambient temperature	18
4.1 Compression test (SAINT-Gobain).....	18
4.2 Particles blasting test (Saint-Gobain).....	18
4.3 Resonance Acoustic Mixer test (RAM) (DLR).....	20
4.4 Particle-to-particle abrasion (CIEMAT)	22
5 Abrasion testing at high temperature	24
5.1 Rotary furnace test at 1000°C (DLR).....	24
5.2 Particle impact test at 950°C (DLR/CIEMAT)	25
6 CONCLUSIONS	32

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Exposure of particles to 1000°C in alumina crucibles in muffle furnace	6
Figure 2: Solar-weighted absorptance of the different particle types during exposure up to 4000 hours to 1000°C.	7
Figure 3: Thermal emittance at 900°C of the different particle types during exposure up to 4000 hours to 1000°C.	7
Figure 4: Spectral absorptance change during exposure of state-of-the-art sintered bauxite particles (left) and FerOX particles (right) to 1000°C during 4000 hours.	8
Figure 5: Spectral emittance change during exposure of state-of-the-art sintered bauxite particles (left) and FerOX particles (right) to 1000°C during 4000 hours.	8
Figure 6: SEM/EDS analysis of as-received FerOx particles (left) and after 3400 hours of exposure to 1000°C (right)	9
Figure 7: SEM/EDS cross-section analysis of as-received FerOx particles (left) and after 3400 hours of exposure to 1000°C (right).....	9
Figure 8: SEM/EDS cross-section of the three coatings on GEN 3 particles after 4000 h of isothermal aging.....	10
Figure 9: SEM/EDS cross-section of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 4000 h of isothermal aging.....	10
Figure 10: Thermocyclic exposure test rig at DFI and photos of samples after the dwell at 1000°C taken during the cooling period.....	12
Figure 11: Solar absorptance of coated granulated (a) GEN 3 and (b) GEN 4 particles as a function of thermocyclic exposure duration.....	13
Figure 12: SEM/EDS cross section of the different coatings on GEN3 particles before and after thermocyclic exposure for 855 h.....	14
Figure 13: SEM/EDS cross section of the three coatings on GEN 3 particles after 3000 h of thermocyclic exposure.....	15
Figure 14: SEM/EDS cross section of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 900 h (300 x3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure.	16
Figure 15: SEM/EDS cross section (top) and surface images (bottom) of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 3000 h (1000 x3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure.....	17
Figure 16: solar-weighted absorptance (left) and thermal emittance (right) after 960h of exposure to the condensation test for 5 different particle types.	17
Figure 17: solar-weighted absorptance (left) and thermal emittance (right) after 960h of exposure to the humidity-freeze test for 5 different particle types.	18
Figure 18: Compression tests results	18
Figure 19: Impact test device.....	19
Figure 20: Particles projected on the stainless-steel target.....	19
Figure 21: GEN4 particles impact tests	20
Figure 22: SEM micrographs of GEN4 particle surface in as-received condition and after coatings.....	21
Figure 23: Spectral absorptance of GEN4 particles after RAM tests.....	21
Figure 24: EDS mapping of the coating layers before and after RAM tests.....	22
Figure 25: a) The adapted Taber oscillating abrasion tester used to evaluate the effect of abrasion due to the interactions between the particles. b) Test tube containing coated Gen3 particles after 100 abrasion test cycles b).....	22
Figure 26: Variation of the α_s value with the number of abrasion cycles in coated Gen3 particles (a) and in coated FerOX Gen 4 particles (b).	23

Figure 27: Rotary kiln furnace and experimental set-up for high temperature abrasion test..24
 Figure 28: Mass loss due to the abrasion for GEN 4 and three types of coatings after 2 hours of rotary kiln furnace experiment24
 Figure 29: Optical measurement after rotary kiln furnace experiment.....25
 Figure 30: High temperature abrasion setup to test particle-to-particle abrasion at 950°C26
 Figure 32: Target with the mask to measured the absorptance of the particles.26
 Figure 31: Variation of the solar absorptance with the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coatings. The values were measured without the black mask.....27
 Figure 33: Variation of the solar absorptance with the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coatings. The values were measured with the black mask.....27
 Figure 34: Decay of the solar absorptance with the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coatings. The values were measured with the black mask.28
 Figure 35: Microscopic images before (left) and after 3 cycles (right) of DFI-coated GEN4 particles, tested in the high temperature abrasion setup.....28
 Figure 36: SEM/EDS analysis of as-received DFI-coated GEN4 particles (left) and after 1 cycle (right) in the high temperature abrasion setup.29
 Figure 37: Changes of the particles after the impacts. (a) is DLR coating, (b) is CIEMAT coating, and (c) is DECHEMA coating. The blue cycles mark partial breakages.....30
 Figure 38: Comparison of the final state with the initial state. Image (a) illustrates the differences between the two states. Green values indicate a difference near zero. Image (b) represents the initial state (orange line) and the final state (blue area).31
 Figure 39: Variation of the solar absorptance of Gen 3 and Gen 4 with the number of impacts and years simulated. The values were measured with the black mask.31
 Figure 40: Changes of Gen3 particles with DECHEMA coating after the impacts and a particle with different cracks.....32

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: % mass loss of as-received and coated GEN4 particles after room temperature abrasion tests.....20
 Table 2: Solar weighted absorptance of as-received and coated GEN4 particles before and after RAM tests.....21
 Table 3: Summary of particle properties34

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

COMPASsCO2	Components' and Materials' Performance for Advanced Solar Supercritical CO2 Power Plants
CST	Concentrating Solar Thermal
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DFI	Dechema Forschungsinstitut
RT	Room Temperature

1 ABSTRACT

This deliverable describes the various durability tests conducted on the different particle types and their coatings examined within the CompassCO₂ project. Four grades of bauxite based state-of-the-art proppants were used as reference particles. Saint-Gobain developed two generations of novel fused particles (consisting of a mix of different oxides), and four generations of granulated particles (of Fe₂O₃ based composition). The fourth generation of granulated particles is also called FerOx. In addition, three types of coatings have been developed by DLR, CIEMAT and DFI to boost solar absorptance. Further information on the novel particles types and their coatings can be found in Deliverables 2.1¹ and 2.2².

The tests described in this deliverable can be divided into three categories: thermal tests (comprising static and cyclic exposure in furnaces), environmental tests (simulating the influence of humidity and freezing) and abrasion tests (at ambient and operational temperature). In the following chapters, each test condition and the obtained results for the different particle types are described in detail.

2 THERMAL EXPOSURE TESTING (DLR/CIEMAT)

2.1 STATIC THERMAL TESTING IN FURNACE UP TO 4000H AND 1000°C

100 gram of each novel particle type including their coatings have been exposed in a Nabertherm LT 40/12 muffle furnace for long-term high temperature testing up to 4000 hours at 1000°C (Figure 1). State-of-the-art bauxite proppants were tested under the same conditions as reference. The solar absorptance and thermal emittance of the exposed particles was measured according to the SolarPACES guideline³.

Figure 1: Exposure of particles to 1000°C in alumina crucibles in muffle furnace

The results of the optical measurements throughout exposure are shown in Figure 2 to Figure 3. State-of-the-art proppants show a strong optical degradation within the first 500 h of testing (both for solar-absorptance and thermal emittance). On the contrary, the Granulated GEN2

¹ Deliverable 2.1 of the CompassCO₂ project: Particle optimization by surface treatment.

² Deliverable 2.2 of the CompassCO₂ project: Particle optimization by modifying chemical composition

³ SolarPACES Guideline "Method to evaluate the reflectance, absorptance and emittance of particles for concentrating solar power technology" Version 1, May 2022. Available online: <https://www.solarpaces.org/csp-research-tasks/task-annexes-iea/task-iiisolar-technology-and-advanced-applications/>

and GEN3 are very stable. GEN4 (also called FerOX) shows slight fluctuations but is also quite stable. The coatings also show quite promising results, maintaining stable absorptance and only DFI coating shows slight thermal emittance degradation.

Figure 4 shows a direct comparison between state-of-the-art proppants and GEN4 in terms of spectral absorptance. The graphs remark that GEN4 achieves about one order of magnitude lower solar absorptance loss than the state-of-the-art proppants after 4000 h of testing. Also the spectral emittance shown in Figure 5 shows significantly less degradation.

Figure 2: Solar-weighted absorptance of the different particle types during exposure up to 4000 hours to 1000°C.

Figure 3: Thermal emittance at 900°C of the different particle types during exposure up to 4000 hours to 1000°C.

Figure 4: Spectral absorptance change during exposure of state-of-the-art sintered bauxite particles (left) and FerOX particles (right) to 1000°C during 4000 hours.

Figure 5: Spectral emittance change during exposure of state-of-the-art sintered bauxite particles (left) and FerOX particles (right) to 1000°C during 4000 hours.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show microscopic analysis before and after exposure of the GEN4 particles to 1000°C for 3400 hours. It can be concluded that GEN4 presents very stable surface and microstructure characteristics. Only minimum changes in terms of increasing surface roughness and pore coalescence can be observed.

Figure 6: SEM/EDS analysis of as-received FerOx particles (left) and after 3400 hours of exposure to 1000°C (right)

Figure 7: SEM/EDS cross-section analysis of as-received FerOx particles (left) and after 3400 hours of exposure to 1000°C (right)

Figure 8 and Figure 9 depict the microstructural changes of the three coating types after 4000 hours of exposure to isothermal aging for GEN 3 and GEN 4 based particles; respectively.

Figure 8: SEM/EDS cross-section of the three coatings on GEN 3 particles after 4000 h of isothermal aging

SEM/EDS analysis of thermally aged samples point out coherent findings with the optical measurements. To begin with, GEN3 particles with DLR and CIEMAT coatings do not show a significant change when compared with as-coated EDS mappings (see Figure 12). In consistency with slight solar absorptance degradation, DFI coating exhibits a slight alteration compared to the as-coated initial state (see Figure 12) by disappearance of Cu rich layer and enrichment of Cr at the surface.

In the case of GEN4 coatings, as can be observed in Figure 9, the presence of the coating layer is confirmed with “Cu” elemental mapping for all types of coatings after 4000 h aging at 1000 °C.

Figure 9: SEM/EDS cross-section of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 4000 h of isothermal aging

In comparison with the as-coated EDS mappings, coating layers remained stable for all types of coatings, as indicated by promising optical measurements. To wrap up, despite the slight

decrease of solar absorptance of GEN 3 DFI coating, which is still around 0.95, all three types of coatings applied on GEN 3 and GEN 4 particles can be considered as stable in terms of their long term high temperature stability under isothermal conditions.

2.2 CYCLIC THERMAL TESTING IN FURNACE UP TO 3000H AND 1000°C (DFI)

In real plant conditions, the particles are exposed to thermocyclic conditions due to the heating in the receiver from e.g. 200 °C up to 900 °C in a few minutes and the heat transfer to the tubes upon entering and exiting the heat exchanger. Such thermocyclic conditions lead to thermally induced stresses in the coating due to the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients; thereby possibly resulting in coating damage such as crack formation and/or spallation. In order to assess the coating degradation under such conditions, thermocyclic exposure tests were planned within this task. The dwell temperature of 1000°C was selected so that the degradation under thermocyclic conditions can be later compared with the isothermal conditions (see furnace ageing tests conducted at the Plataforma Solar de Almeria in collaboration with CIEMAT and DLR, section 2.1). Moreover, it was decided by the WP2 consortium that the particle samples can be cooled to a minimum temperature such as RT to aggravate the superimposition of thermally induced stresses to the stress-state within the coating at the highest extent.

Thermocyclic exposures of coated granulated GEN 3 and GEN 4 particles (three coatings: DFI, DLR and CIEMAT for both generations) were conducted in alumina crucibles in a test apparatus equipped with a horizontal alumina furnace tube by DFI at 1000°C with 3 h dwell time followed by a compressed air cooling (see Figure 10). The furnace was calibrated before the exposure test and the temperature was continuously measured and controlled within ± 5 K during exposure using a Type-S thermocouple. The cycle starts with the movement of the furnace towards the particles. The heating period lasts 11 minutes (to reach 97% of the dwell temperature according to ISO 13573:2012). After 3 h at the holding temperature, the furnace moves in the opposite direction and the cooling period of 30 min involving the activation of the compressed air cooling (2.5 bar pressure), via a magnetic switch, starts. The cooling period of 30 min is sufficient to cool down the particles below 50°C again as prescribed by ISO 13573:2012. Due to the well-known limited machinability of alumina, a rather small opening (in-house geometry adaptation via automated diamond saw cutting by the mechanical shop of DFI) of the furnace tube (see Figure 10) can be achieved, through which the compressed air cooling is applied. Therefore, only a limited number of samples, namely only the coated GEN 3 and GEN 4 particles (without their uncoated counterparts) could be included in the thermocyclic exposure tests.

A total duration of 3000 h (1000 x 3h cycles) have been completed for both particle generations with the abovementioned coatings. After certain intervals of 855 h, 1725 h and 3000 h were

taken out and shipped to CIEMAT for the measurement of solar absorptance and to DLR for the post-exposure characterization.

Figure 10: Thermocyclic exposure test rig at DFI and photos of samples after the dwell at 1000°C taken during the cooling period.

The solar absorptance of the coated particles after thermocyclic exposure is shown in Figure 11. Unequivocally, all three coatings led to a significant increase in the solar absorptance of both particle generations in the as-deposited condition. The improvement of the solar absorptance for both particle generations with coatings was higher for DFI and CIEMAT coatings. However, during thermocyclic exposure, a slight degradation of the solar absorptance was observed for DFI and CIEMAT coated GEN 3 particles. On the contrary, the DLR coating showed a notable increase in terms of absorptance similar to the exposure in isothermal conditions (see Figure 2). This behavior can be associated with the completion of the heat treatment during the high temperature exposure for the DLR coating. The reduction of the solar absorptance for the DFI coating on granulated GEN 3 over the exposure duration (see Figure 11.a) was attributed to the presence of metallic Cr-particles within the coating (confirmed by EPMA measurements, not shown here) and their oxidation during thermocyclic exposure. This led to the consequential formation of chromia within the coating and resulted in a decrease in the absorptance. It was probably caused by a cross-contamination of the sieves used for the coating process and was solved by the utilization of new sieves for the manufacturing process of the GEN 4 coatings. A similar degradation was also observed for the CIEMAT coatings, but to a lesser extent compared to DFI coatings on GEN 3 particles. This can be explained by the stabilization of different spinel phases for the CIEMAT coated GEN 3 particles over time.

Unlike GEN 3 particles, DFI coatings on GEN 4 showed a highly stable behavior and maintained their high solar absorptance around 97 % for 3000 h of thermocyclic exposure similar to the isothermal conditions (see Figure 2). The stable behaviour of the DFI coating GEN 4 particles supports the aforementioned hypothesis of cross-contamination effects during the manufacturing of coatings on GEN 3 particles. CIEMAT coatings exhibited a comparable trend with the DFI coatings and did not show a degradation of absorptance during 3000 h of thermocyclic exposure. Similar to their behavior on GEN 3 particles, DLR coatings showed a notable increase within the early stages of the exposure and thereafter exhibited a stable behavior.

Notwithstanding above, it is clear that all three coatings increased the absorptance of both particle generations significantly. Especially for GEN 4 particles, all coatings showed a highly stable behavior for 3000 h of thermocyclic exposure which is in good agreement with the results of the isothermal exposure (Figure 2). In the following section, post-exposure characterization of the coated particles will be elucidated for a better understanding of their behavior on both generations of particles.

Figure 11: Solar absorptance of coated granulated (a) GEN 3 and (b) GEN 4 particles as a function of thermocyclic exposure duration.

Figure 12 shows the cross sectional images of the three coating on GEN 3 particles prior to and after 855 h (285 x3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure. Comparative SEM/EDS mappings of GEN 3 coatings in as-coated and after thermocycling tests explains the changes in the solar absorptance values. Thermal cycling acted as a further sintering stage for the GEN 3 DLR coatings rather than degradation. EDS mappings before and after shows better crystallization and integration of the coating layer, which results in increased solar absorptance. In the case of DFI, Cr-rich oxides are detected after thermal cycling (not shown here), which explains the slight decrease in solar absorptance values. CIEMAT coating has also lower solar absorptance after thermocycling, which is due to the diffusion of the coating constituents through inner parts of the particle, especially through the glassy phase canals, as can be seen in SEM/EDS mapping.

Figure 12: SEM/EDS cross section of the different coatings on GEN3 particles before and after thermocyclic exposure for 855 h.

Figure 13 depicts the cross sectional images of the investigated coatings after the maximum thermocyclic exposure duration of 3000 h. The stable behavior of DLR coating over time can be explained by the maintenance of the coating layer (best visible by the Cu-distribution map). On the other hand, diffusion of aluminium from the particles to the coating layer evidently led to the stabilization of different spinel phases for the other two coatings and changed the coating composition. This can explain the degradation of their solar absorptance over time. For the CIEMAT coating, Fe- and Al-enrichment above the coating layer can be observed. Particularly, for the DFI coating, the absence of a homogeneous Cu-rich coating layer after 3000 h of exposure should be noted. Furthermore, the presence of metallic Cr-particles in the as-deposited DFI coatings due to the aforementioned cross-contamination and their oxidation during exposure clearly led to a further reduction in the absorptance.

Figure 13: SEM/EDS cross section of the three coatings on GEN 3 particles after 3000 h of thermocyclic exposure.

Figure 14 illustrates the cross sectional investigation of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 900 h (300 x 3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure at 1000°C. Unlike the DFI coatings on GEN 3 particles, the coating layer was maintained for the DFI coating on GEN 4 particles (best visible by the Cu-map). The initial coating thickness appears to be higher for GEN 4 particles. Similar to the DFI coating, the CIEMAT coating was also able to maintain the Cu-rich layer and did not exhibit the diffusion of other cations from the particles to the coating layer. For the DLR coating, evidently, the improvement of absorptance was related to the additional heat treatment provided by the exposure.

Figure 14: SEM/EDS cross section of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 900 h (300 x3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure.

Figure 15 shows the post-exposure characterization of the investigated coatings on GEN 4 particles after the maximum thermocyclic exposure duration of 3000 h. Clearly, all coatings were able to maintain a pigment-rich coating layer after 3000 h (visible by the Cu-maps).

Figure 15: SEM/EDS cross section (top) and surface images (bottom) of the three coatings on GEN 4 particles after 3000 h (1000 x3h cycles) of thermocyclic exposure

3 ENVIRONMENTAL TESTING (CONDENSATION AND FREEZING CONDITIONS) (DLR/CIEMAT)

100 g of pristine SB30/50 proppants have been exposed together with coated and non-coated FerOx particles in climatic chambers for 960 hours to check their interaction at prolonged times with humidity and under cyclic freezing conditions. The two conducted environmental tests are standardized in ISO 6270-2CH (=condensation test at 100% relative humidity and 40°C) and IEC 62108 (=humidity freeze test, cyclic exposure between -40 and +85°C at 97% of relative humidity). State-of-the-art bauxite proppants were tested under the same conditions as reference. The solar absorptance and thermal emittance of the exposed particles was measured according to the SolarPACES guideline.

As can be seen in Figure 16 and Figure 17, all particles show excellent resistance against condensation and humidity-freeze conditions. We conclude that environmental conditions at ambient temperatures will have negligible impact on the particle or coating durability.

Figure 16: solar-weighted absorptance (left) and thermal emittance (right) after 960h of exposure to the condensation test for 5 different particle types.

Figure 17: solar-weighted absorptance (left) and thermal emittance (right) after 960h of exposure to the humidity-freeze test for 5 different particle types.

4 ABRASION AND MECHANICAL TESTING AT AMBIENT TEMPERATURE

4.1 COMPRESSION TEST (SAINT-GOBAIN)

The breaking force was measured on the particles after sieving between 0.8 mm and 1 mm. The particles were crushed between two tungsten carbide plates and the breaking force was measured and recorded for each particle (20 particles analysed).

Figure 18: Compression tests results

The results are presented in the Figure 18. From one generation to another one, the mechanical properties were improved gradually. And for the new developed particles, the highest mechanical properties were achieved for the granulated particles GEN4. The mechanical properties are in same range compared to the state-of-the-art BL 16/30 with a breaking force around 140N.

4.2 PARTICLES BLASTING TEST (SAINT-GOBAIN)

Mechanical strength of the particles was analysed using a particle blasting facility. The particles are tested thanks to a home-made shot peening device. This impact test operates

in a closed loop. The particles (100g) are accelerated in a tube by an air flow (pressure 2bars) and impacted on a rigid target (stainless steel target). After 5 minutes (around 60 cycles), the beads are sieved and the amount of fragments is evaluated. The device used is presented in the figure below.

Figure 19: Impact test device

Figure 20: Particles projected on the stainless-steel target

The particles are sieved between 0.85 and 1 mm before measurements. The particles size distributions before and after the impact tests and the ratio of breakage are presented in the figure below. We can see that the GEN4 particles present quite similar behaviour to the state-of-the-art. Ratios of breakage of 43.7 and 50.5 % were found respectively for the GEN4 and for the state-of-the-art particles.

Figure 21: GEN4 particles impact tests

4.3 RESONANCE ACOUSTIC MIXER TEST (RAM) (DLR)

After successful coating of new GEN4 particles, coatings of DLR, DFI and Ciemat on those particles were tested in terms of their room temperature abrasion resistance. For this purpose, resonance acoustic mixer (RAM) was used. During this test particles are filled in a closed plastic vessel and exposed to 80 g acceleration inducing particle-particle collisions for 15 minutes. Afterwards, the particles were removed and washed with de-ionized water in ultrasonic bath to remove the debris away. After drying, the mass loss due to the abrasion was recorded. In addition to three coated GEN4, as-received GEN4 was also tested for direct comparison purposes.

% mass losses after RAM tests are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: % mass loss of as-received and coated GEN4 particles after room temperature abrasion tests.

Mass loss	GEN4	GEN4 DLR	GEN4 DFI	GEN4 CIEMAT
(%w.t.)	1.6	0.46	0.53	2.38

When compared with as-received GEN4 particles, after DLR and DFI coatings, lower mass loss due the abrasion was observed, indicating improvement of surface properties by coating. In the case of Ciemat coated GEN4 particles, relatively higher mass loss was observed. All three institutions use different coating methods, different pigment types in varying amounts, which makes a direct quantitative comparison difficult. Therefore, for a better understanding, surface investigation and absorbance values are required.

As-received and coated GEN4 particles were analyzed by SEM in low-vacuum conditions to be able to obtain details of the surface properties as given in Figure 22.

Figure 22: SEM micrographs of GEN4 particle surface in as-received condition and after coatings

For all three types of coatings, successful coverage of GEN4 particle surface can be observed in Figure 22. In the case of CIEMAT coating, a significant surface roughness with bigger chunks of coating was observable. These poorly attached coating pieces may be the reason of the relatively higher mass losses after RAM. Beyond mass loss and microstructural findings, the samples after RAM tests were also investigated in terms of their solar absorptance as given in Figure 23 and Table 2.

Figure 23: Spectral absorptance of GEN4 particles after RAM tests

Table 2: Solar weighted absorptance of as-received and coated GEN4 particles before and after RAM tests

Solar weighted absorptance	GEN 4	GEN 4 DLR	GEN4 Dechema	GEN4 CIEMAT
Before RAM	0.83	0.927	0.970	0.965
After RAM	0.82	0.916	0.973	0.950

Solar absorptance measurement indicates, after 15 minutes of severe abrasion conditions in RAM, there is no significant loss. Cu mappings of as-coated and RAM tested GEN4 particles with coating also in parallel with the spectrometric findings.

Figure 24: EDS mapping of the coating layers before and after RAM tests

Despite some minor changes, all coating types remained stable after RAM room temperature abrasion tests as can be observed in Figure 24.

4.4 PARTICLE-TO-PARTICLE ABRASION (CIEMAT)

A Taber oscillating abrasion tester (Model 6160) has been adapted to evaluate the effect of abrasion due to interactions between the particles. This equipment, originally designed to rub the sample under study with an abrasive agent such as sand or other compound that acts as an abrasive, was modified to study the damage produced in particles by the oscillating cyclic movement. A pad with three compartments for test tubes has been introduced in the original device in order to test several samples at the same time. Three glass tubes filled with 7 mL of coated particles were subjected to the cyclic oscillating movement. The cycle speed applied was 100 cycles per minute, accumulating several cycles up to a maximum of 10000. From time to time, the particles were removed and optically characterised. Figure 25 shows a picture of the equipment.

Figure 25: a) The adapted Taber oscillating abrasion tester used to evaluate the effect of abrasion due to the interactions between the particles. b) Test tube containing coated Gen3 particles after 100 abrasion test cycles b)

With this equipment, GEN 3 and GEN 4 FerOx particles coated by the three partners (DLR, DFI, and CIEMAT) were evaluated. Figure 26 shows the results with the average values of three measurements.

(a)

(b)

Figure 26: Variation of the as value with the number of abrasion cycles in coated Gen3 particles (a) and in coated FerOX Gen 4 particles (b).

The highest initial solar absorptance value on Gen 3 was 0.98 (CIE coating), followed by the DFI coating and DLR coating. An interesting effect was observed in the CIE and DLR coating, as this value increased after the first measurements. This was explained by an increase in the coating surface roughness produced by particle collisions. The solar absorptance decreases around 1 percentage point after 10000 abrasion cycles, remaining an important part of the coatings on the surface of the particles.

In the case of FerOx particles, the highest initial solar absorptance was obtained with the DFI coating, and similar decay of the initial value with the abrasion cycles was observed in the three coatings.

The abrasion test developed here is not a realistic test, as the temperature is far lower than under operational conditions, but it is a good option to compare coatings and study the coating thickness reduction produced by collisions among particles.

5 ABRASION TESTING AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

5.1 ROTARY FURNACE TEST AT 1000°C (DLR)

In order to mimick the particle-particle collisions at elevated temperatures within the particle receiver and in the transport tubes between CSP plant components, rotary kiln furnace was used as represented in Figure 27. In a typical test, 15 grams of particles was inserted into a corundum crucible, which was covered by a feld to inhibit the particles loss. Corudum crucible with particles were inserted into the rotary kiln furnace with an inclination of 5 degrees.

Figure 27: Rotary kiln furnace and experimental set-up for high temperature abrasion test

1000°C with a rotation speed of 15 rpm was employed for 2 hours. At the end of the experiment, particles were collected washed in ultrasonic bath to ensure removal of the debri. After drying at 80°C, dry particles were weighed to evaluate the mass loss as given in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Mass loss due to the abrasion for GEN 4 and three types of coatings after 2 hours of rotary kiln furnace experiment

Mass loss values plotted in Figure 28 indicate high temperature abrasion resistance of GEN4 particles is slightly lower than state-of-the-art bauxite particles. Presence of harder ZrO₂ grains in GEN4 particles may result in this slightly higher mass loss due to the abrasion of GEN4 particles when they collide with each other. The abrasion resistance of the three types of coatings was also evaluated in a comparative manner, where CIEMAT exhibits the lowest mass loss. Due to the different coating methods and varying amount of pigment used, it may not be representative to compare mass loss directly. Solar weighted absorptance was used to evaluate abrasion resistance of coatings. Solar absorptance of particles do not exhibit a significant degradation when compared with as-coated vales. All coating types can be considered as stable under rotary kiln furnace experiment conditions. The solar weighted absorptance is 0.847, 0.927, 0.957, 0.952 for granulated Gen4, Gen4+DLR coating, Gen4+Ciemat coating and Gen4+Dechema coating after the experiment, respectively.

Figure 29: Optical measurement after rotary kiln furnace experiment

5.2 PARTICLE IMPACT TEST AT 950°C (DLR/CIEMAT)

A new setup to mimic high-temperature particle-to-particle attrition at 950°C and up to 5 m/s impact velocities was designed and constructed (see Figure 30). The particles to be investigated, were glued to a alumina (Whipox) target using a Al₂O₃ binder. Each cycle with 2 kg of falling particles result in ≈ 2100 impacts per target particle, which simulated around 2.9 years of operation (assuming that the particles run twice per day through the receiver).

The particles tested were the Gen4 with CIEMAT, DECHEMA, and DLR coatings. The particles were subjected to a series of tests until they reached the impacts corresponding to a 10-year operating period (7300 impacts).

Figure 30: High temperature attrition setup to test particle-to-particle attrition at 950°C

The solar absorptance of the particles glued to the target was measured after different amounts of impacts using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050 spectrophotometer. The measurement was challenging due to the white background to which the particles were glued. In order to reduce the influence of the background on the absorptance measurement, a black mask with a hole was employed during the measurement, as seen in Figure 31. Despite the use of the mask, the substrate still influenced the measurements. Consequently, the measured value was less than the actual absorptance of the particle.

Figure 31: Mask used for the absorptance measurements in the spectrophotometer.

The results of the optical measurements without mask are presented in Figure 32. It shows a relatively low absorptance loss for the DLR and CIEMAT coatings, while the DECHEMA coating exhibited a greater decline.

The values measured with mask are presented in Figure 33, confirming the same trend as the measurements without mask. Since the absolute values can not be trusted due to the influence of the white background, it is best to analyze the relative loss of solar absorptance compared

to its initial value (see Figure 34, the data with mask was used to compute the relative loss). The results demonstrate a reduction in solar absorptance of 10.00% for the DEHEMA coating. In contrast, the DLR and CIEMAT coatings exhibited a more modest decline, with a reduction of 1.82% and 1.35%, respectively.

Figure 32: Variation of the solar absorptance with the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coated particles. The values were measured without the black mask.

Figure 33: Variation of the solar absorptance with the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coated particles. The values were measured with the black mask.

Figure 34: Relative solar absorptance loss plotted over the number of impacts and years simulated for the different coated particles. The values were measured with the black mask.

Figure 35 shows Gen4 DECHEMA coated particles before and after ~2920 impacts or 4 years of simulation. For only few particles local partial particle breakage is observed. The color change from black towards the reddish color after exposure indicates partial coating removal due to attrition.

The surface SEM/EDS analysis conducted in Figure 36 confirms the partial coating removal, revealed by the high superficial Al-content after exposure.

Figure 35: Microscopic images before (left) and after about 2920 impacts per particle (right) of DECHEMA-coated Gen4 particles, tested in the high temperature attrition setup.

Figure 36: SEM/EDS analysis of as-received DECHEMA-coated Gen4 particles (left) and after 2100 impacts in the high temperature attrition setup.

Photographs of the particles were taken after each cycle, as shown in Figure 37. It was observed that the color of the particles became progressively brighter with each cycle. As expected, the CIEMAT particles exhibited the darkest hue after simulating 10 years of operation. A notable partial break was observed after 9 years of simulation, which subsequently expanded in the following test (marked in red in Figure 37). The appearance of the DECHEMA coating corresponds to the measured absorptance loss in the spectrophotometer, with the coating appearing brighter after 10 years of simulation due to large brown-toned areas compared to the other coatings. In contrast, the DLR coating appeared brighter than CIEMAT, with smaller areas exhibiting brown tones compared to the DECHEMA coating.

Figure 37: Changes of the particles after the impacts. (a) is DLR coating, (b) is CIEMAT coating, and (c) is DECHEMA coating. The red circles in (b) mark partial breakages.

Despite the observed changes in absorptance and the presence of minor breakage in Figure 37, there is minimal evidence of surface alteration for any of the coatings. This is likely due to the hardness of the particle. Figure 38 provides an illustration of two particles without coating before and after testing. The observed differences in Figure 38 are likely due to the inherent limitations of the 3D measurement.

Figure 38: Comparison of the particle profile before and after testing. Image (a) illustrates the differences between the two states represented by a heat map. Green values indicate a difference near zero. Image (b) represents the initial state (orange line) and the final state (blue area).

In order to compare the behaviour of the Gen3 to the Gen4 particles, a target with Gen 3 and DECHEMA coating was tested. Figure 39 presents the measured relative absorptance loss. After ten years of simulated operation, the absorptance values of the Gen3 coated particles were found to be similar to coated Gen4 particles.

Figure 39: Evolution of the solar absorptance loss of Gen 3 and Gen 4 particles coated with DECHEMA coating with the number of impacts and years simulated. The values were measured with the black mask.

A comparison of Figure 37c and Figure 40 shows a greater number of broken particles for Gen3 than for Gen 4. This is attributed to the lower mechanical strength of the Gen3 particles. The broken particles can be observed as brighter area within the particle. During the tests, a cracked particle was observed after 5.88 years of simulation.

Figure 40: Changes of Gen3 particles with DEHEMA coating after the impacts and a particle with different cracks.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the results of several durability tests to qualify the performance of novel particle developments compared to state-of-the-art proppants.

Two long-term **thermal tests** have been conducted at 1000°C, one under static and one under cyclic conditions, up to 4000 and 3000 hours respectively. The static exposure showed that the novel granulated particles achieve about one order of magnitude lower solar absorptance loss than the state-of-the-art proppants after 4000 h of testing. The microstructure of the granulated particles remains stable after testing. Also the coatings on granulated Gen3 and Gen4 particles achieve to maintain stable optical properties and to maintain a pigment-rich coating layer after both, static and cyclic testing. The DLR coating even slightly improves the solar absorptance throughout testing, indicating that the applied heat treatment after deposition was not sufficient to finalize the curing.

Regarding **environmental testing**, all examined particles show excellent resistance against condensation and humidity-freeze conditions. We conclude that environmental conditions at ambient temperatures will have negligible impact on the particle or coating durability.

Regarding **abrasion and mechanical testing at ambient temperature**, it is worth mentioning that the mechanical properties of the granulated particles have been improved gradually throughout the generations by Saint-Gobain until Gen4 reached the same range as the state-of-the-art proppants (breaking force around 140N). In the particle impact test as well as the Gen4 particles present quite similar behaviour to the state-of-the-art in terms of the ratio of breakage.

Regarding the **abrasion resistance of coated particles at ambient temperatures**, two tests have been conducted. Despite some minor changes, the three coating types remained stable after Resonance Acoustic Mixer testing for 15 minutes. In the particle-to-particle abrasion test, an absorptance loss of 1 to 1.5% has been measured for coated Gen3 and Gen4 particles, indicating that the three coatings show similar abrasion resistance.

Regarding **abrasion testing at operational temperature**, it can be observed that despite the lower absorptance of Gen4, it is a superior option to Gen3 due to its stable shape and low particle breakage throughout the tests. It is possible to enhance the absorptance through the use of different coatings. The lowest absorptance loss was observed for the CIEMAT coating,

which has also a high initial absorptance (96.7%, similar to the coating from DFI) and retains its coating on the particle after attrition testing at 950°C and rotary kiln furnace testing at 1000°C. The absorptance loss of the DLR coating is slightly larger than the one of the CIEMAT coating, followed by the DFI coating.

Based on the above mentioned results and also on the particle properties determined throughout the project (see Table 3), the granulated Gen4 particles were identified as the most promising ones for commercialization due to the low manufacturing cost and good mechanical properties. These particles are obtained by granulating waste products from the steel industry and can therefore be produced cost-effectively at a cost of only approx. 1 €/kg. The granulated particles have similarly good mechanical and optical properties compared to the sintered particles previously used in the fracking industry. They surpass the state of the art in terms of a higher energy density (2.2 J/(cm³·K) compared to approx. 2.0 J/(cm³·K)) and a higher softening temperature (940 °C compared to approx. 850 °C). **Saint Gobain then decided to market the new particles under the name FerOx.** The particle properties highlighted in red in Table 3 indicate that the particle does not meet the defined target value; the numbers highlighted in green indicate that the target is achieved. As can be seen, FerOx meets all the targets except for the solar-absorptance. In combination with coatings, the solar absorptance can be boosted up to 97%. However, the application of a coating is estimated to increase the cost significantly (about 50 to 75 cents per kilo). It remains an optimization question, depending on the specific use case or receiver design, to evaluate if the increase in absorptance compensates for the higher cost.

Table 3: Summary of particle properties

Property	Target values	State of the art proppants					Coatings on Gen 4						
		Sintered Bauxite SB 30/50	BauxLite BL 16/30	BauxLite BL 30/50	InterProp IP 30/50	Fused Gen 1	Fused Gen 2	Granulated Gen 2	Granulated Gen 3	Granulated Gen 4	CIEMAT Coating on Gen 4	DECH coating on Gen 4	DLR coating on Gen 4
Size distribution [µm]		297-590	590-1190	297-590	297-590	800-1200	600-1200	600-1250	600-1200	600-1200	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Cost [€/kg]	<1	1.5	<1.5	<1.5	<1.5	5	3	3	~1.3 - 1.5	~1	~0.5 - 0.75	~0.5 - 0.75	0.54
c_p at 1000°C [J/g·K]	>1.1	1.28	1.16	1.11	1.07	1.20		0.88	Similar to Gen2	1.1	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Bulk density ρ_b [g/cm ³]	>2	1.85	1.74	1.61	1.73	2.08	2.08	2.8	2.83	2.0	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Material density ρ_m [g/cm ³] specific /absolute	>3.5	3.3/3.45	3.06/3.42	3.12/3.26	3.16/3.34	3.47/3.53	3.32/3.39	4.71/5.07	4.92/5.04	3.56/3.76	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Softening temperature T_s [°C]	>900	882	857	850	856	1110	1080	1010	1080	940	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Vickers Hardness $HV_{0.1}$	>900	911	833	623	723	1110	988	636	704	926	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Breaking force F [N] 0.8-1.0mm	>140		141			63	98	70	90	120-140	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Sphericity [-] B/L (Q3=50.0 %)	as good as proppants	0.87	0.87	0.86	0.86	0.94	0.95	0.91	0.86	0.89	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Roundness [-]	as good as proppants	0.75	0.72	0.71	0.76	0.79	0.81	0.79	0.81	0.82	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4	Same as Gen 4
Solar absorptance α [-]	>0.9	0.845	0.914	0.851	0.834	0.964	0.974	0.928	0.882	0.833	0.967	0.970	0.926
Thermal emittance ϵ at 900°C [-]		0.757	0.845	0.767	0.737	0.951	0.941	0.829	0.772	0.614	0.809	0.931	0.708